

Data Management Checklist for Project Close or Researcher Off-Boarding

This checklist is a guide for researchers at all career stages leaving University College Cork, or for projects during the completion or close-out phase of the project. It aims to ensure that the data/outputs produced by the researcher and/or project are properly managed. This includes documentation and metadata, storage internally within UCC and sharing of data/ outputs as FAIR and Open Data, and those outputs and retention periods required for compliance with the [UCC Code of Research Conduct](#) retention policy.

Please note that your UCC One Drive will be deleted 30 days after you leave UCC for more information visit [UCC IT Services Storage Options](#).

This document is adapted from Naeem Muhammad, Researcher Offboarding Checklist (Zenodo: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7520528>) licensed CC-BY-4.0. Several similar and useful documents are provided in the reference list below.

This document is also licensed under a CC-BY-4.0 license
<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

Please cite as Thorpe, D., & Coffey, A. (2024). Data Management Checklist for Project Close or Researcher Off-Boarding. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10453935>

1. Who are you and what research have you been doing?

Name	
Role	
Project/ Lab	
Project lead/ supervisor	
Data Owners (including those outside of UCC)	
Departure Date	
Project close date if relevant	
Data taken over by	
Are you aware of IT policies regarding leaving UCC and access to accounts and storage?	
Do you need access to the data after you leave UCC?	Yes [] No []
How will this be enabled?	

Have you migrated/transferred data from your device(s) or One Drive to a shared storage area?	Yes [] No []
What platform will you migrate the data/outputs to?	
Have you transferred ownership of any Team/SharePoint/other storage location to an appropriate person?	Yes [] No []
Have you provided a 'readme' file for each meaningful cluster of data? (this could be for just one file, or could be for multiple related files) [Cornell University have provided a useful 'readme' template]	Yes [] No []
What is the naming convention for files and folders?	
Are the data/outputs well documented and supported by rich metadata?	Yes [] No []
If relevant, have you provided relevant code with the data?	Yes [] No [] N/A []
Is the code annotated and documented?	Yes [] No [] N/A []
Do you have a website / web resource?	Yes [] No [] N/A []
Will it be archived post project or before you leave UCC?	Yes [] No [] N/A []
If it remains available/live for how long post project or after you leave UCC?	
Do you need to transfer ownership (for researchers leaving UCC)?	Yes [] No [] N/A []
Who will take responsibility for the website?	

Will it need continued maintenance and how are these provided for? (e.g. domain cost, editing and other maintenance) [For more on web archiving, see Thorpe (2023), 'How to preserve, cite, and design websites for the long-term future']	Yes [] No [] N/A []
Do data/outputs include data which is sensitive due to GDPR?	Yes [] No []
Is the documentation for ethical approval provided with the data?	Yes [] No [] N/A []
Will you anonymise the data? If no, then why not?	Yes [] No [] N/A []
Do you need to convert proprietary file formats to open ones for preservation?	Yes [] No []
Do you have a Data Management Plan (DMP)? If yes, have you fulfilled the commitments made and complied with all legal and ethical requirements and data sharing (FAIR/Open Data) outlined in the DMP? (e.g. Licensing, access levels, anonymisation etc.)	Yes [] No [] Yes [] No []

2. What data do you have?

List dataset/outputs by name in the table below. Give a brief description of the content, size and format and location for each object. Add more rows if necessary.

Data/Output Name	Description	Size	File Format	Current Location	Who will this be handed over too?

3. Where is the data going?

If you are a researcher leaving a project before it has been completed the following sections may not be relevant, however please read and fill in if applicable.

List any outputs shared or to be shared as FAIR and Open Data and provide a Persistent Identifier if available.

Name and Data Description	Location	DOI/PID (if already published)	License
	<i>e.g. Zenodo</i>		

Any datasets or outputs shared as FAIR data in repositories which meet the retention policy of the UCC Code of Research Conduct and/or the funding body do not need to also be retained within UCC. However, records and data not suitable for sharing as FAIR data must be retained within UCC in line with the UCC Code of Research Conduct or funder requirements.

List data/outputs, records which will not be shared but maintained as internal records and give a deletion date.

Name and Data Description	Location for archival storage	Deletion date	Person responsible for deleting the data

Any other comments, notes or questions that need to be addressed:

References

- Briney, Kristin A. (2020) *Project Close-Out Checklist for Research Data*. [Teaching Resource] (Unpublished) <https://resolver.caltech.edu/CaltechAUTHORS:20200519-142758925>
- Goldman, Julie; Jessica Pierce; Sarah Hauserman. (2022). Research Data Management Onboarding Checklist: Comprehensive Version. OSF. <https://osf.io/zwxr7>
- Muhammad, Naeem. (2023). Researcher Offboarding Checklist (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7520528>
- UW-Madison, Research Data Management Offboarding Checklist. (2020?): <https://researchdata.wisc.edu/wp-content/uploads/2020/06/OffboardingChecklist.pdf>
- Thorpe, Deborah. (2023). *How to preserve, cite, and design websites for the long-term future*, The River-Side. [Blog]: <https://perma.cc/Y35Y-XQH5>